

SFERALARDA KOMMUTATIV KILLIN VEKTOR MAYDONLARI HAQIDA

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ANNOTATSIYA

Killing vektor maydonlari differensial geometriya, boshqaruv nazariyasi va nazariy fizikaning turli sohalari muhim o‘rin egallaydi. Ular silliq ko‘pburchaklarda (manifoldlarda) izometriyalar guruh harakatlarini hosil qiladi va ushbu vektor maydonlari oilasi uchun erishiluvchanlik (attainability) sohalari ushbu orbitlarning geometriyasi orqali ifodalanadi. Ushbu maqolada Evklid fazosidagi Killing vektor maydonlarining xossalari foydalanilgan holda sferalarda ularning orbitalari tadqiq etiladi. Berilgan vektor maydonlari oilasining shartlariga qarab, orbitalarning turlari va ular bo‘ylab kovariant differensialning xossalari aniqlanadi.

KALIT SO‘ZLAR

killing vektor maydonlari, differensial geometriya, izometriyalar, silliq ko‘pburchak (manifold), orbit, erishiluvchanlik sohasi, kovariant differensial, Evklid fazosi, sferalar.

О КОММУТИРУЮЩИХ КИЛЛИНГОВЫХ ВЕКТОРНЫХ ПОЛЯХ НА СФЕРАХ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Киллинговы векторные поля являются одними из важнейших векторных полей в прикладных областях дифференциальной геометрии, качественной теории управления и физики, поскольку они порождают групповое действие изометрий на гладких многообразиях, а геометрия их орбит отражает множества достижимости семейства киллинговых векторных полей на этих многообразиях. Используя свойства киллинговых векторных полей в евклидовых пространствах, мы исследуем орбиты семейства киллинговых векторных полей на сферах. В зависимости от условий заданного семейства можно определить типы орбит и свойства ковариантных производных вдоль данных киллинговых векторных полей.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА

киллинговы векторные поля, дифференциальная геометрия, изометрии, гладкие многообразия, орбиты, ковариантная производная, евклидово пространство, сфера.

ON THE COMMUTING KILLING VECTOR FIELDS ON THE SPHERES SAITOVA SAYYORA

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ABSTRACT

The Killing vector fields are the most important vector fields in numeric areas of differential geometry, qualitative control theory and physics, as they generate the group action of isometries on the smooth manifolds and the geometry of their orbits represents the attainability sets of the family of Killing vector fields on the manifolds. Using the properties of Killing vector fields in Euclidian spaces we investigate orbits of the family of Killing vector fields on the spheres. According to conditions of a given family we can define types of the orbits and properties of covariant differential along given Killing vector fields.

KEYWORDS

killing vector fields, differential geometry, isometries, smooth manifolds, orbits, covariant derivative, Euclidean space, spheres.

Introduction.

The most actual researches for vector fields on Riemannian manifolds have become the subject of numerous investigations ([1], [4-5], [8], [28-30]). Specifically, in the works of H. Sussman [29-31], K.L.Duggal [7], Lobry [8], Jurjevic [10], Katanayev [33-34] and A Narmanov [17-23] various topological and geometric properties of orbits of a given family of vector fields have been examined and investigated in the sense of geometrical and physical aspects.

Killing vector fields are a special class of vector fields. A Killing vector field is a vector field that generates a symmetry of a manifold. It means that movement of each point along the vector field does not change the distances or angles between points. A Killing vector field satisfies Killing equation, which is a condition on the covariant derivative of the vector field. Killing vector fields are related to the isometries and the Lie algebra of the manifold. The study of transformations that preserve the metric of spacetime plays an exceptionally important role in mathematical physics. Suffice, that these transformations are associated with the most crucial conservation laws. These transformations give rise to what is known as a Killing vector field. In physics, Killing vector fields indicate the symmetry of a physical model and help identify conserved quantities, such as energy, impulse. In the theory of relativity, for example, if the metric tensor does not depend on time, then in spacetime there exists a time-like Killing vector associated with a conserved quantity - the energy of the gravitational field.

M.O. Katanaev has proposed an integrable model of gravity with torsion in two-dimensional spacetime, developed through the method of conformal blocks for constructing global solutions

in gravity for arbitrary two-dimensional metrics admitting a single Killing vector field. In his 2016 work [34], he examines Killing vector fields and homogeneous and isotropic universes, investigating fundamental theorems related to Killing vector fields. Specifically, spaces with constant curvature were considered.

For the proof of the theorems from [36, 22, 27] the results of S. Kobayashi [12] were widely used. In his works, S. Kobayashi proved that the set of fixed points of an isometry group is a totally geodesic submanifold of even codimension. As is known, the infinitesimal transformations generated by a Killing vector field form a one-parameter isometry group.

In this paper we investigate Killing vector fields on spheres in Euclidian spaces. Unless otherwise specified, we obtain spheres with Euclidian metric and appropriate coordinate system. And, our vector fields on the sphere are the rotations with the center coincident with the origin (center of the sphere). All objects, manifolds, mappings and vector fields are supposed to be smooth.

2. Preliminaries. We define the most necessary objects, as Killing vector fields and the properties of a family of the such vector fields.

Definition 2.1. A vector field X on the Riemannian manifold (M, g) is called a Killing vector field, if the infinitesimal transformations $x \rightarrow X^t(x)$, generated by the vector field X are isometries.

Here $X^t(x)$ denotes the point on the integral curve of the given vector field corresponding to the parameter t .

Or, equivalently $L_X g = 0$, where L_X – Lie derivative on (M, g) .

Example 2.2. Let us consider the following vector fields on $R^2(x, y)$:

$$X_1 = \frac{\partial}{\partial x}, \quad X_2 = y \frac{\partial}{\partial x} - x \frac{\partial}{\partial y}.$$

For every point $p(x_0, y_0)$ on the Euclidian plane transformations $p \rightarrow X'(p)$ of these vector fields are given as follows:

$$\begin{cases} x(t) = x_0 + t \\ y(t) = y_0 \end{cases}, \text{ and } \begin{cases} x(t) = x_0 \sin t + y_0 \cos t \\ y(t) = x_0 \cos t - y_0 \sin t \end{cases}$$

The first map is the translation along the axe Ox , and the second one is the rotation around the origin. Both transformations are isometries of the plane. Consequently, these vector fields are Killing vector fields.

The set of all Killing vector fields on a manifold (M, g) is known to be closed under the Lie bracket of two Killing fields, and a linear combination of Killing vector fields over the field of real numbers is also a Killing vector field.

For a Killing vector field X , and λ -real number, the vector field $Y = \lambda X$ is also a Killing vector field, as the integral curves of the vector fields coincide as sets, only differing in their traversal speed. In this case, it is easy to verify $[X, Y] = 0$ for Lie brackets of those pair of Killing vector fields.

Frequently, in mathematical physics models, the problem of finding Killing vectors for a given metric on a manifold are investigated. Each Killing vector field is associated with a one-parameter group of transformations, which in this case preserves the metric.

Proposal 2.3. [34] Let $(M; g)$ the Riemannian manifold and it has $N \leq \dim M$ nonzero commuting and independent Killing vector fields $K_i, i = 1, \dots, n$. Then there exists a coordinate system in which all metric components do not depend on N coordinates corresponding to Killing trajectories. Inversely. If, in a certain coordinate system, the components of a metric do not depend on N coordinates, then the metric allows at least N commuting Killing vector fields.

According to the stated statement, in the limiting case where the number of Killing commuting fields is equal to the dimension of the manifold, i.e. $N = n$, there is a coordinate system in which all components of the metric are constant.

If a Riemannian manifold has two or more noncommuting Killing vector fields, this does not mean that there is a coordinate system in which the components of the metric do not depend on two or more coordinates.

Therefore, the set of all Killing vector fields on the manifold (M, g) denoted as $K(M)$, forms a Lie algebra over the field of real numbers. Furthermore, it is known that the Lie algebra of Killing vector fields on a connected Riemannian manifold (M, g)

has a dimension no greater than $\frac{1}{2}n(n+1)$, where n -is the dimension of (M, g) ([2]).

Example 2.4. Let us consider the 2-sphere $S^2 \subset R^3$. The metric on the sphere g induced via immersion $i: S^2 \rightarrow R^3$. Riemannian manifold $(S^2; g)$ has three Killing vector fields, according the group $SO(3)$ of the rotations of Euclidian space R^3 . These rotations are noncommuting.

It is easy to show that there is no local coordinate system on a sphere in which the components of a metric do not depend on two coordinates. Indeed, this means that in a given coordinate system, the components of the metric are constant, and therefore the curvature is zero. But this is impossible, because the curvature of the sphere is constant and non-zero.

Definition 2.5. [39] Define the orbit $L(x)$ of the family of vector fields D through the point x , as the set of points y from M , for those exist the real numbers t_1, t_2, \dots, t_k and vector fields $X_{i_1}, X_{i_2}, \dots, X_{i_k}$ from D (for all natural k) such as: $y = X_{i_k}^{t_k} (X_{i_{k-1}}^{t_{k-1}} (\dots (X_{i_1}^{t_1} (x)) \dots))$.

Theorem 2.6. ([39], 64 pp). Let X, Y are smooth vector fields on manifold M , then for every point $p \in M$ the curve $Z^t(p) = Y^{-\sqrt{t}} (X^{-\sqrt{t}} (Y^{\sqrt{t}} (X^{\sqrt{t}} (p))))$ is smooth for enough small $t \geq 0$, and Lie bracket of these vector fields is tangent to this curve at $Z^0(p) = p$:

$$[X, Y]_p = [X, Y](p) = \left. \frac{d}{dt} \right|_{t=0} Z^t(p)$$

Theorem 2.7. ([13]). Let X, Y are smooth vector fields on manifold M . Then the condition

According to the proposals above if $q = p$ during the motion along the given vector fields, we say the vector fields are commuting, i.e.

$$X^t(Y^s(p)) = Y^s(X^t(p))$$

$X^t(Y^s(p)) = Y^s(X^t(p))$ is equivalent to $[X, Y] = 0$, for all $t, s \in \mathbb{R}^1$ and $p \in M$.

Let X, Y be smooth vector fields on a manifold M . So in local coordinates we express the vector fields through basic fields, i.e.:

$$X = \sum_{i=1}^n \xi^i(x) \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i} \text{ and } Y = \sum_{i=1}^n \eta^i(x) \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i},$$

From those coordinates we calculate new vector fields with i -coordinate function as follows:

$$a_i = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\xi^j \frac{\partial \eta^i}{\partial x^j} - \eta^j \frac{\partial \xi^i}{\partial x^j} \right)$$

The final vector field is Lie bracket (commutator) of vector fields X and Y

Example 2.8. Let us given the following (Killing) vector fields

$$X = -y \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + x \frac{\partial}{\partial y}, Y = (x+1) \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + y \frac{\partial}{\partial y}.$$

The result after the calculation of their Lie brackets is: $[X, Y] = -\frac{\partial}{\partial y}$.

3. On the commuting Killing vector fields. According to the investigations given in [36, 22, 27] the invariant subspace of the rotations in Euclidian space has dimension $2k$, the space of the fixed points has dimension $n-2k$, and according to the S.Kobayashi ($n-2k$) is even. Also, the origin is the center of our sphere. Further, in our research we investigate such rotations on spheres (see example 3.1).

Example 3.1. In the four dimensional Euclidian space two Killing vector fields are given:

$X = \{-y, x, 0, 0\}, Y = \{0, 0, -\omega, z\}$. Hence $X^1 = -y, X^2 = x, X^3 = 0, X^4 = 0$ and $Y^1 = 0, Y^2 = 0, Y^3 = -\omega, Y^4 = z$ when $Z = [X, Y]$. Calculating coordinates of the Lie bracket we have: $[X, Y](x, y) = Z(x, y) = \{0; 0; 0; 0\}$. Although the all coordinates are zero, these vector fields are commuting.

Such irreducible rotations of the Euclidian space are also rotations on the corresponding spheres. The main goal of this work is investigating such rotations, i.e. Killing vector fields on the spheres.

Example 3.2. Let us consider three dimensional sphere in the 4-dimensional Euclidian space $S^3 \subset \mathbb{R}^4$ given as $x^2 + y^2 + z^2 + w^2 = 1$; where x, y, z, w –Cartesian coordinates in \mathbb{R}^4 .

On the sphere S^3 , Killing vector fields X, Y are given:

$$X = -y \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + x \frac{\partial}{\partial y} - w \frac{\partial}{\partial z} + z \frac{\partial}{\partial w}, Y = -z \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + x \frac{\partial}{\partial z}$$

Lie bracket $[X, Y]$ of vector fields X, Y is:

$$[X, Y] = -w \frac{\partial}{\partial x} - z \frac{\partial}{\partial y} + y \frac{\partial}{\partial z} + x \frac{\partial}{\partial w}$$

Hence such Killing vector fields are not commuting, and more than fields $X, Y, [X, Y]$ are belongs to the minimal subalgebra $A(D)$, contains given vector fields.

In the point $p(1, 0, 0, 0) \in S^3$ vectors $X(p), Y(p), [X, Y](p)$ are linearly independent, i.e. the subspace $A_p(D) = \{X(p): X \in A(D)\}$ has

dimension three. And the orbit $L(p)$ has dimension three too. According to Theorem 1 ([21]) the orbit $L(p)$ is a closed subset. On the other hand, due to the theorems from ([22]) as the orbit has maximal dimension, $L(p)$ is an open subset of S^3 . Though, orbit coincides with S^3 .

On the base of theorems from [36] we know that rotations has even dimensional invariant

subspaces. When rotation is irreducible and it's invariant subspace goes through the origin, for spheres we have the sections of such invariant subspaces and the sphere, hence the invariant subset of rotation is the circle of the maximal radius, i.e. totally geodesic submanifold. The set of fixed points of such rotations are invariant subspace too, and due to Theorem of S.Kobayashi it has even codimension. So, the set of fixed points of Killing vector field on the Sphere is the sections with such subspaces.

Theorem 3.3 [36]. *Let us X, Y - the Killing vector fields generating the rotations in the Euclidian space (we call them “rotations”), and N_1, N_2 are the set fixed points of rotations, and the same time (singularities for “rotations” X and Y). Then the Killing vector fields X and Y are commuting if either $\dim N_1 = \dim N_2 = 0$ or $R^n = N_1 \oplus N_2$.*

Notation. *The case with $\dim N_1 = \dim N_2 = 0$ we won't consider.*

The statements from [36] gives us the

Corollary 3.4. *Linearly independent rotations of Euclidian space are commuting only for even dimensions of the space.*

And it is known that $S^n \subset R^{n+1}$. And if $(n+1)$ is even, naturally we have

Corollary 3.5. *Linearly independent “rotations” of a sphere in Euclidian space are commuting only for odd dimensions of the sphere.*

$$g(\nabla_X X, Y) + g(X, \nabla_X Y) = 0. \text{ Lets continue our calculations: } g(X, \nabla_X Y) = 0. \text{ So}$$

$$g(\nabla_Y X, Y) + g(X, \nabla_Y Y) = 0, \quad g(Y, \nabla_Y X) = 0, \text{ or } g(X, \nabla_X Y) = 0, \quad g(Y, \nabla_X Y) = 0$$

Let us denote $Z = \nabla_X Y$ and we have $g(X, Z) = 0$ and $g(Y, Z) = 0$, so vector field Z is orthogonal to X, Y . Let us suppose $Z \neq 0$ then $Xg(X, Z) = g(\nabla_X X, Z) + g(X, \nabla_X Z) = 0$ and X orthogonal to $\nabla_X Z = \nabla_X^2 Y$ and for every $s = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots$: $g(X, \nabla_X^{(s)} Y) = 0$

And as we supposed “rotations” X and Y have orthogonal invariant subspheres, it means that $\nabla_X^{(s)} Y$ belongs to N_1 and if among them enough linearly independent vector fields Y_1, Y_2, \dots, Y_m such as $Y = Y_1 + Y_2 + \dots + Y_m$ for finite s , and $\nabla_X^s Y \in N_1$. $\dim N_1 \leq n-1$, so if $s > \dim N_1$ we have $\nabla_X^s Y = \lambda \nabla_X^{s-1} Y$, we denote $Z_l = \nabla_X^l Y$, $l = 1, 2, \dots, s$.

Let $Z_l \in N_1$ and Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_l be a basis on N_1 then $Y = \alpha_1 Z_1 + \alpha_2 Z_2 + \dots + \alpha_n Z_n$

$\nabla_X Y = \alpha_1 \nabla_X Z_1 + \alpha_2 \nabla_X Z_2 + \dots + \alpha_n \nabla_X Z_n$, and by our notation

$Z_1 = \alpha_1 Z_2 + \alpha_2 Z_3 + \dots$, so it's covariant derivative

$\nabla_X Z_1 = \alpha_1 \nabla_X Z_2 + \alpha_2 \nabla_X Z_3 + \dots$. By repeating this action we have

$Z_2 = \alpha_1 Z_3 + \alpha_2 Z_4 + \dots$, and so on... $Z_{s-1} = \alpha_1 Z_s$.

Now Z_1, Z_2, \dots, Z_s - are linearly depend and that is contradiction to definition of basis on

N_1 .

The invariant subspace of our rotations are orthogonally complement to the subspace of fixed points.

Corollary 3.6. *Invariant subspaces of linearly independent “rotations” on the sphere in Euclidian are orthogonally circles of maximal radius, i.e. orthogonally totally geodesic submanifolds of the sphere.*

In the Riemannian geometry, on the Riemannian manifold (M, g) with riemannian metric g , Levi-Chivita connection “nabla” for commuting Killing vector fields, whose trajectories are the geodesic we have the following statements:

$L_X g = 0$, i.e. $Xg(Y, Z) = 0$ for X - Killing vector field and $\forall Y, Z$ - smooth vector fields, for all, but we consider only Killing vector fields. So

$Xg(Y, Z) = g(\nabla_X Y, Z) + g(Y, \nabla_X Z)$, and for orthogonal vector field: X and Y also

$g(X, Y) = 0$. In the same time

$[X, Y] = \nabla_X Y - \nabla_Y X$, as vector fields are

commuting: $\nabla_X Y = \nabla_Y X$. And for tangent vector

field X - to geodesics we have $\nabla_X X = 0$.

Using these conditions for Killing vector field:

$Xg(X, Y) = 0$ and $Yg(X, Y) = 0$, and

In general the trajectories of the rotations are not necessary the geodesic, so we have to consider another constructions for the condition of the commuting Killing vector fields on the sphere. As we know the flow generated by our rotations is the isometry in the Euclidian space, and on the statements from [40] isometries have the form of “cell”, each “cell” describes the motion on according invariant space of given Killing vector field. Thus changing the coordinate system by choosing the coordinate planes as invariant spaces of given vector field we have: coordinate functions of given commuting Killing vector fields on the Sphere has no the same coordinates. That means their covariant derivations is zero (by elementary calculation formula).

Hence, we have proved

Theorem 3.8. The given Killing vector fields (“rotations”) X, Y on the sphere are commuting iff

$$\nabla_X Y = 0 \text{ and } \nabla_Y X = 0.$$

The properties of the rotations on the sphere and the method of calculations are useful for investigation the controllability via two Killing vector fields on the Sphere (see [11], [14], [19], [25], [27]). So we may constructs the following vector fields a their orbit coincides the given Sphere:

$$X = \{-x_2, x_1, -x_4, x_3, \dots\} \text{ and } Y = \{0, -x_3, x_2, -x_5, x_4, \dots\}.$$

According the classifications the orbits of a family of Killing vector fields given in [36,38,27], the proved Theorem 3.8 and the analyzing the given examples we conclude:

Corollary 3.9. The orbits of a family of Killing vector fields on the Sphere are the spheres and tori of some dimension.

Notation 3.10. The dimension of spheres and existence of tori are defend from the point on sphere and the odd or even dimension of the Sphere.

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